

ISic1574

Fragmentary funerary inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8824

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]οιοδιο[---]

Apparatus

Text after Brugnone

Manni Piraino, [οἴμ]οι ὄ Διο

Translation

Commentary

It is tempting to restore the typical Selinuntine formula of οἴμοι ὄ + vocative, but caution is advised by Brugnone

Digital identifiers:

TM 284901

EDR 112482

EDCS 41300080

PHI 175694

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 96

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At C1 tav.14.67

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